

**INNOVATIVE TECHNIQUES FOR EDUCATIONAL COMMENTING
STORIES BY A.S. PUSHKIN "THE CAPTAIN'S DAUGHTER"**

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ANNOTATION

In addition to using the technique of commented reading, which is successfully used in the methodology of teaching literature, we consider it necessary to introduce into teaching practice new techniques that are not yet used or are insufficiently used in literature lessons. One of the components of the system of commented reading of a literary work, according to our assumptions, should be the identification of the peculiarities of the perception of the text using the two-part diary technique. Another component of the system is commenting as a control over the effectiveness of assimilation of the text; its task is to identify how deeply the student understood the work, whether he was attentive during the lesson, listening to the teacher's comments.

Key words: *Comments, creativity, changes, analysis, A.S. Pushkin, M.D. Kocherin, G.I. Belenky, M.A. Shneerson, OK. Bogomolov.*

Let us dwell in more detail on the course of the experiment and some of its results. In the course of our work, we were faced with the following tasks: to find out. [1. p. 8-9]

1. Do new teaching techniques contribute to the development of the ability to express thoughts and impressions about the text?
2. Do schoolchildren develop a personally significant attitude towards the work (did he relate this topic to himself)?
3. Do new commenting techniques stimulate increased attention to the text?
4. Does this technique affect the development of the student's speech abilities?
5. Do new working methods develop the creative abilities of schoolchildren?

6. Does it help to return to the text and re-evaluate it?

Let us show what data were revealed when using new techniques for commenting on the story by A.S. Pushkin "The Captain's Daughter" in the 8th grade of gymnasium school No. 12 in Bishkek.

30 students took part in the experiment.

Students studied this story in the middle of the second quarter of eighth grade. At the beginning of our experimental lesson, students answered the following questions:

1. Which episode from the story by A.S. Did Pushkin's "The Captain's Daughter" impress you the most?
2. What life lessons have you learned?
3. What literary hero do Pyotr Grinev and Pugachev remind you of?
4. What was the scariest thing in the story for you?

An encounter with a work of art should fundamentally be pedagogically prepared, purposeful in forming the most adequate perception possible. Creating an attitude towards reflective and empathic reading of a literary text arouses not only interest in the work, but also a certain direction of perception. The preparatory work is designed to stimulate a certain minimum range of associations that are important for perception, to involve in the essence of the problems, and to outline the path along which the reader will move. [2. p. 38-39]

One way to encourage reading is to bring students' personal experiences to life. M.A. Rybnikova advised "preparing reading with living impressions." It is important that, immersing himself in his own experiences and memories, the student will be able to later, when analyzing the work, find an associative connection between his emotions, thoughts, ideas and images and actions of the heroes of the work.

In our practice, work with text was preceded by the creation of student essays on the topic: "I choose...". Reading aloud such miniature essays created a special confidential and emotional atmosphere at the beginning of the lesson. In this way, the personal situation of reading the work was organized and deepened.

As an example of an essay, we offer several works by students of the 8th grade of gymnasium school No. 12.

One day my parents were getting ready to divorce, and my mother gave me a choice: stay with her or live with my dad. At that moment I fell into severe depression. But then, thank God, everything worked out - the parents made peace. (Alexandra Krasienko)

It was recently. At a dance competition, our club was condemned by the jury because they were persuaded. At the previous competition we performed better than other couples in our city, and at this competition the second place was taken by a couple who then could not even get to the finals.

In general, before the competition we were gathered for voting. We had a choice:

- ignore this competition and leave,
- go to the competition, no matter what.

I decided to stay because I love dancing, competing with other couples, and besides, my love was at this competition. Nothing could make me leave! (Ilya Chu)

I have a lot of friends and girlfriends in my yard. They always invite you to go outside for a walk. But I fall short in my studies and I need to study a lot and a lot. If I refuse to go out with my friends, they get offended and call me a nerd, and I don't like that. It turns out that I am between two fires and I have to choose: chat with friends or learn lessons, because in the future I will be nowhere without knowledge. On my mother's advice, I study in the evenings. I'll do my homework and go see my friends. (Kemel kyzy Saikal) [3. p. 124-125]

My friend Yulia was very fond of a boy whose name is Rodion. But even though Julia was beautiful, he didn't like her, just as he loved me. So he offered me friendship. I didn't know what to answer him, because I liked him too. I delayed answering for a long time, because my friend might be offended by me. All three of us suffered because it turned out to be a love triangle. In the end, I decided that my friend was more valuable to me, and there would still be guys. (Lera Zueva)

It is obvious that immersion in personal memories tunes in to a certain emotional wave, opens the soul slightly, making it more receptive to analyzing the actions of the characters. This is "thematically" oriented emotional and personal training.

The next technique used in the lesson was working with a two-part diary. "A two-part diary is an interactive method of working with text. It involves recording the reader's thoughts, comments, evaluations, etc. according to a certain scheme: quotes are written in one part, comments on them in the other" (30, 148). We used this technique to identify the peculiarities of schoolchildren's perception of A.S.'s story. Pushkin "The Captain's Daughter". Let us show how the "two-part diary" technique is used when analyzing a fragment of the scene "Pugachev's Court".

Students write down the fragments that most impressed each of them and comment on them in writing. This stage of work lasts 15-20 minutes.

A fragment of the scene “Pugachev’s Court” is expressively read aloud, then read sequentially, with stops. All students who have comments on specific phrases introduce them to the class. Here are some comments on the above scene:

32% of schoolchildren commented on the words of Captain Mironov, who refused to swear allegiance to Pugachev. 26% were delighted with Grinev’s action. 18% assessed Savelich’s actions. 12% paid attention to Grinev’s prayer.

After analyzing the students’ work, we came to the conclusion that their understanding of the text is most often superficial. From their point of view, the characters of the heroes are unilinear, namely: Pugachev is a villain, Grinev is a hero, Savelich is either a hero or a coward. From the works presented above, it is clear that some schoolchildren did not understand the hero’s actions (for example, A. Krupnov’s commentary). Guidelines for using the “two-part journal” technique advise that the teacher “...avoid speaking in an authoritarian tone, ask questions about what people thought or felt, guide, encourage students to comment on each other’s opinions, use non-verbal cues, allowing time for silence and time for waiting for an answer” (35, 20). [4. p. 31-33]

To analyze a work to promote a deeper understanding, student comments alone are not enough. For example, Pugachev’s robe or the mutilated Bashkir man attracted the attention of students during independent reading. In addition, due to insufficient development of analysis skills and age-related characteristics of perception, they were not able to see in the text some important things for its understanding.

The help of a teacher is needed to explain the meaning of unclear words, to focus on details important for understanding the meaning of the story, etc. (A sample commentary is given in the appendix to the thesis).

The lesson also used visual commentary: different artistic solutions to the same episode: reproductions from paintings: V.G. Perov. Pugachev's court (1875), S.V. Gerasimov. “The Captain's Daughter” (1950), G.S. Dmitriev “The Captain’s Daughter” (1983) (See Appendix 2. - A.Ch).

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